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Herbert Bruderer

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Books

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 2. Auflage 2018

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 1. Auflage 2015

Konrad Zuse und die Schweiz, 1. Auflage 2012

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- Bruderer, Herbert [2018a]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 2. Auflage 2018, Band 1, 751 Seiten, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110520705>
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- Bruderer, Herbert [2020c]: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the German by John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

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